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Decent Work in Scotland: Thematic Report 1

What Scotland's future workforce think about 'Decent Work'

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- A Research and Knowledge Exchange linking UWS academics and Oxfam and its community partners in collaborative projects;
- A programme of placements and work-related learning and volunteering opportunities, enabling UWS students to contribute to the work of Oxfam and its community partners, while learning and developing their experience and skills;
- The UWS-Oxfam Policy Forum, which brings all of these partners together with a broad range of external organisations from across all sectors of Scottish society, to discuss key questions and to inform understanding and engagement with both existing and emergent issues.

The Partnership publishes a series of Collaborative Research Reports, which are published on the Partnership's website www.uwsoxfampartnership.org.uk.

WHAT SCOTLAND'S FUTURE WORKFORCE THINK ABOUT 'DECENT WORK'

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This study investigates 82 Scottish secondary school pupils' views on and expectations about decent work.

- The majority expect to get decent work when they leave school
- Participants view decent jobs as jobs that will allow them to live comfortably and be financially independent
- Good bosses and friendly colleagues are valued
- Young people identify the importance of equality and fair treatment in the workplace, and expect they will experience this when they start working
- Most are confident they will get in-work training
- A substantial number of young people believe their future jobs will be valued and worthwhile
- Young people believe they should be protected from exploitative and unsafe work

WHAT WE DID

This report is one of a series produced for the UWS-Oxfam Partnership which explores the notion of 'decent work' from a number of perspectives. This particular report focuses on exploring Scottish secondary school pupils' perceptions and expectations of the adult world of work. One might argue that school students are the furthest away from the jobs market in comparison to other groups. While this is undoubtedly the case in respect of the adult job market, research has shown that having experience of paid part-time work prior to leaving school is a common experience in Scotland, as Howieson, McKechnie and Semple (2006) showed. Their large scale, representative study demonstrated that just under half of all pupils had part-time work experience prior to reaching the end of compulsory schooling.

Investigating the views of those not yet able to join the adult labour market is an important undertaking as, similar to research with adults, research with teenagers has demonstrated the important link between the quality of the employment experience and a range of developmental outcomes, including psychological health (O'Brien & Feather, 1990), job satisfaction and healthy work-related attitudes (Loughlin & Barling, 1998). Recently the 'scarring effect of unemployment' on young people has also been acknowledged (McQuaid, 2015).

For this research project, eighty-two secondary school pupils from eight schools located in the West of Scotland area participated in 16 focus groups between September and December 2015. They were aged between 13 and 17. Most (85%) were below the compulsory school leaving age. More females (63%) than males (37%) participated. In contrast with Howieson et al., (2006) and others, in this study, the majority of the sample (84%) had never experienced paid part-time work. Only eight pupils were currently employed in part-time work, while a further five had past experience. The majority therefore had no direct experience of work.

Each focus group combined group discussion with written workbook and 'card sort' activities. Pupils were asked to reflect on what characteristics of work they felt would make a job good or bad. Their expectations of the world of work were sought via a short opinion survey. Survey questions were designed to reflect the International Labour Organisation's [ILO] indicators of decent work (ILO, 2008). The card sort activity also utilised these definitions and asked pupils to rate each of the measures in order of importance on a 9-point scale (Figure 1). The group could place cards anywhere they liked on the board. Pupils were additionally asked to consider how employers, parents, schools and government could help them obtain decent work post-secondary school.

What are young people's expectations of the world of work?

Students were asked in the survey about their expectations of the world of work. The results generally describe a positive, indeed optimistic view of the workplace and what it can offer them in the future. The statements which follow indicate their views on what work beyond school will be like.

- A high proportion of respondents (59%) either agreed or strongly agreed that the job they will get on leaving school will be 'decent'. Only 7% disagreed.
- 88% thought that the job they will do when they leave school will be 'valued by society and socially worthwhile'.
- When addressing whether their future work will be 'stable and secure', 69% either agreed or strongly agreed, only 2.5% disagreed. 12% believed they would be subject to a zero-hour contract, 61% expected not to be.
- 82% expected to be working in a safe environment, no-one expected not to be.
- With regard to working time, 52% thought that they would get regular hours 'at a time that suits me', 12% thought not; while 69% were positive that the hours of work would allow them to enjoy a personal life, 2.5% disagreed.
- 83% agreed or strongly agreed that the job would pay them 'enough to live on'. Only 1% of the sample were pessimistic about this. Pupils were less confident (but mainly positive) about their prospects of receiving equal pay - 75% felt they would: 16% felt they wouldn't. Males (86%) were surer of this than females (69%).
- In respect of paid holidays, 57% thought they would get paid holidays. However, 43% were unsure of this, suggesting a lack of understanding of pay and holiday arrangements in the workplace.
- 71% were sure they would not experience discrimination in the workplace. 12% thought they would, while 17% were unsure.
- Most were confident they would get training in the workplace (72%).
- 56% were sure their employers would be understanding if they were sick, however 34% were uncertain of this.
- A similar proportion, (36%) were unsure if their employer would listen to their problems; however most (63%) felt that they would.
- 65% agreed or strongly agreed that their voices would help shape their future work but a third (29%) were uncertain.
- In consideration of future employment opportunities, 21% believed it would be easy to get a job on leaving school, while 33% believed it would not be easy. The remainder (46%) were unsure of their future employment prospects.

These results suggest that young people expect many of the features of what could be considered decent work to be in place when they enter employment after school. Pupils believed their future jobs will be valued, stable and safe. Pay will be adequate for independent living and training will be provided. Conditions of work and pay will be fair and without discrimination. In contrast some benefits of work, such as paid holidays, were less recognised, which perhaps suggests a lack of understanding of the detail of being an employee among young people still in school. Pupils were similarly uncertain about whether their employers would listen to their problems or be understanding about sickness absence. A significant uncertainty surrounded their future employment prospects with almost half unsure of their post-school job opportunities. Nevertheless, overall, school students held positive expectations of the adult workplace.

REFERENCES

- Howieson, C., McKechnie, J., and Semple, S. (2006). *The Nature and Implications of the Part-Time Employment of Secondary School Pupils*. Edinburgh: Scottish Executive.
- Loughlin, C., and Barling, J. (1998). Teenagers' part-time employment and their work-related attitudes and aspirations. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 19, 197–207.
- McQuaid, R. (2015, June 12). *Multiple scarring effects of youth unemployment*. Paper presented at the Skills Development Forum, Skills Development Scotland, Glasgow, Scotland.
- O'Brien, G. E., and Feather, N. T. (1990). The relative effects of unemployment and quality of employment on the affect, work values and personal control of adolescents. *Journal of Occupational Psychology*, 63, 151–165.
- ILO. (2008). [International Labour Organisation.] *Measurement of Decent Work*. Available online: www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---dgreports/---integration/documents/meetingdocument/wcms_115402.pdf

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